

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE REGARDING CHOLELITHIASIS AMONG NURSES AT PEOPLES MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL, NAWABSHAH

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18810512>

Keywords

Nurses, Knowledge, Cholelithiasis,

Article History

Received: 28 December 2025

Accepted: 13 February 2026

Published: 28 February 2026

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Gallbladder diseases, especially gallstones, are common health problems that often require surgical treatment. Nausea and vomiting are most common postoperative complications after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Suggests that nurses' early assessment and patient mobilization enhance recovery. In Pakistan, prevalence of gallstone disease ranges from 8% in adults over 40 years, and the surgical incidence of cholecystectomy is reported at about 18.4%. study of laparoscopic cholecystectomy shows morbidity rates 6-7% and mortality rates around 0.3-0.4% in high volume centers.

Objective: This study determined the knowledge of cholelithiasis and its associated risk factors at PMCH Nawabshah.

Methodology: This study was the cross-sectional study, in which 250 nurses were selected using non-probability convenience sampling technique, and conducted from September to November 2025 at PMCH Nawabshah.

Results: The study found that many of the nurses had the basic knowledge of cholelithiasis, but few had the limited understanding about the complications. Among male participants, 13(13%) poor knowledge, 20(20%) , moderate knowledge, and (113%) have good knowledge. Moreover, among female participants. The association between gender and knowledge level have statistically significant association ($p = .022$). Age of subject mean 40.5360, the standard deviation 6.21120, the minimum was 30.00, the maximum was 59.00. The male participants were 58.40%, and the females who responses are 41.60%. The number of diploma responders were 128 (51.2%), BSN responders were 109 (43.6%), and MSN/MSPH 13 (5.2%). Years of experience mean 12.11, the median were 11.00, the standard deviation were 5.28, the minimum experience were 2 years, and the maximum were 30 years.

Conclusion: This study conducted that the total of 50% had poor knowledge, 50-70% had moderate knowledge while 75% nurses had good knowledge about its associated risk factors at PMCH Nawabshah.

INTRODUCTION

Gallbladder diseases, especially gallstones, are common health problems that often require surgical

treatment (1). Nausea and vomiting are most common postoperative complications after

laparoscopic cholecystectomy (2). Suggests that nurses early assessment and patient mobilization enhance recovery (3). In Pakistan, prevalence of gallstone disease ranges from 8% in adults over 40 years, and the surgical incidence of cholecystectomy is reported at about 18.4%. study of laparoscopic cholecystectomy shows morbidity rates 6-7% and mortality rates around 0.3-0.4% in high volume centers. Nurses showed lack of knowledge and inadequate practice about dietary management for gallbladder disease, contributing to suboptimal practice. The current study found that many nurses had the low knowledge regarding the patient management with Cholelithiasis, so it's very important to continue education programs to improve the patient's care quality (4). Structured education significantly raised nurses' knowledge and practice scores on post-operative cholecystectomy care. study showed that the educational programs can improve the clinical knowledge in the health care settings(5). Comfort-focused nursing interventions improve postoperative quality of life and reduce negative emotions in surgical patients. Using invocative teaching methods like concept mapping improves the knowledge of nurses regarding perioperative care and ensure patient's comfort and satisfaction(6). Educational programs significantly improved nurses' knowledge and attitudes regarding cholecystectomy care. Simulation based learning was the most powerful learning to improve clinical skills and confidence(8). Nurses are central to ensuring safe and effective recovery after surgery. Their responsibilities include monitoring patients for complication, managing pain, providing wound care, encouraging early ambulation, and educating patients about dietary and lifestyle modifications. Inadequate knowledge or poor practice by nurses can compromise recovery and increase hospital stays. Patient's education programs can improve the patient's understanding of self-care, and reduce the postoperative complications and improve the recovery(9). Self-care education for patients improved knowledge and may reduce readmissions after LC. Pathway nursing and Enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) models significantly improve outcomes and shorten stays after cholecystectomy Individualized nursing interventions reduced perioperative errors and

improved patient safety and satisfaction in laparoscopic cholecystectomy patients(10). Self-learning packages effectively improved nurses' knowledge and observed practice for LC care. Many patients lack practical discharge advice; nurses' counselling crucial and often insufficient. nursing improve the preoperative preparations and reduce the anxiety of the patient, in modern nursing care(11). Nursing research on cholecystectomy is growing, with emphasis on education, Enhanced recovery after surgery ERAS, and patient outcomes shows research gaps in low-resource settings. study showed a growing global interest in nursing research that is related to cholecystectomy(12). In Pakistan, including at PMCH Nawabshah, laparoscopic procedures are now commonly performed. However, structured nursing education programs specific to LC postoperative care are limited. Suggest that protocol-based interventions can optimize patient comfort and satisfaction. Effective pain management can significantly reduce the postoperative discomfort of the patients(13). Reinforces that effective analgesia supports faster ambulation and fewer complications(14).

Aim of Study: To evaluate the level of knowledge among nurses regarding the Cholelithiasis at Peoples Medical College Hospital and to determine its association with the selected demographic variables.

Objectives of Study:

1. To assess knowledge and practice of nurses at PMC Hospital Nawabshah regarding laparoscopic cholecystectomy care.

Material & Methods

This study was the cross-sectional study, in which 250 nurses were selected using non-probability convenience sampling technique, and conducted from September to November 2025 at PMCH Nawabshah. The sample size was calculated by using Rao software sample size calculated with the population of 250 nurses of PMCH the confidence level percent 95% and the margin of error 5% and prevalence was 8% so the sample size was 79%.

Inclusion criteria

1. Registered nurses, 1 year' experience, directly caring for LC patients at PMCH.

2. Both male and female
3. Nurses who are willing to participate

Exclusion criteria

1. Nurses <1 year of experience.
2. Nurses on leave or not involved in direct postoperative care.
3. Nurses who are not working in surgical wards.

Tools for Data Collection:

Structured questionnaire (knowledge). Observational checklist (practice). **Knowledge:** nurse’s knowledge was collected through a short questionnaire. It was included the simple questions about postoperative care after cholecystectomy, like pain control, wound care, and patient, safety. Each nurse completed the form during duty hours with the researchers help if needed. **Practice:** nurses were checked by using an observation checklist. The researchers were quietly observed how nurses perform their daily postoperative care, such as monitoring patients,

changing dressings, and helping with movement. **Attitude:** nurse’s attitude was measured through a few simple statements using a rating scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Their answers showed how they feel about caring for postoperative patients. After data collection, all responses will be reviewed for accuracy and completeness. The data will be coded and analyzed using the statistical package for the social sciences (spss). Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) will be used to summarize demographic data and nurse’s knowledge and practice scores. Inferential statistics, including the paired t-test and chi-square test, will determine the difference between pre and post test results and the relationship between selected demographic variables and outcome scores. Findings will be presented in tables and figures, and p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Distribution of Knowledge level among nurses.

No	Variable	Definition	Poor	Moderate	Good
1	Knowledge	Nurses understanding about postoperative care of patient after LC.	50%	50% to 70%	75%
2	Practice	What nurses actually do while giving postoperative care.	<50%	50% to 75%	>75%
3	Attitude	Nurses feelings and opinions towards postoperative patient care	<50%	50% to 75%	75%

Result

Socio demographic variables

Table No. 01 knowledge

S: no	Items	poor	Moderate	Good	P value
1	Gender of subject				
	Male	13	20	113	.022
	Female	5	28	71	

2	Qualification Diploma BSN MSN/MSPH	13 3 2	33 12 3	82 94 8	.002
3	Marital status Single Married Divorced	5 13 0	2 44 2	23 160 1	.024

Among male participants, 13 (8.9%) had poor knowledge, 20(13.7%) had moderate knowledge, and 113(77.4%) had good knowledge. Among female participants, 5 (4.4%) demonstrated poor knowledge. 33(27.5%) had moderate knowledge, and 82 (68.2%) had good knowledge. The association between gender and knowledge level was not statistically significant (p = 0.022). With respect to educational qualification, participants with a Diploma in Nursing showed 13

(6.0%) cases of poor knowledge, 44 (20.3%) moderate, and 160(73.7%) had good knowledge. Among BSN participants, 3((2.8%)) had poor knowledge, 12(11.0%) moderate, and 94 (86.2%)good knowledge. MSN/ MSPH participants demonstrated 2(15.4%) poor: 3(23.1%) moderate, and 8 (61.5%)good knowledge, The Association between educational qualification and knowledge level was not statistically significant (p = 0.002).

**Table No.02. Distribution of age of subject:
Age of subject**

MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	MIN	MAX
40.5360	6.21120	30.00	59.00

Age of subject mean 40.5360, the standard deviation 6.21120, the minimum was 30.00, the maximum was 59.00.

Graph No.01. distribution of gender of subject:

Majority of Study population were male (54.40%)

Table no.03. distribution of qualification of subject qualification of subject

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Diploma in Nursing	128	51.2
BSN	109	43.6
MSN/MSPH	13	5.2
Total	250	100.0

The number of diploma responders were 128 (51.2%), BNS responders were 109 (43.6%), and MSN/MSPH were 13 (5.2%).

Table no.04. distribution of years of experience

Years of experience

minimum experience were 2 years, and the

Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
12.11	5.28	2 years	30 years

Years of experience mean 12.11, the median were 11.00, the standard deviation were 5.28, the

maximum were 30 years.

Table no.06. distribution of age of subject

s.no	Item	yes	no	P value
1	Cholelithiasis means there is a formation of stones in gallbladder	241 (96.4%)	9 (3.6%)	.010
2	Can Cholelithiasis affect the organ named gallbladder.	235 (94%)	15 (6%)	.005
3	Obese person has higher risk of gallstones	234 (93.6%)	16 (6.4%)	.054
4	Can gallstones directly proportional to family history	194 (77.6%)	56 (22.4%)	.218
5	Pain of gallstones occurs in upper quadrant of abdominal	232 (92.8%)	18 (7.2%)	.168
6	Pain usually occurs after having fatty meal.	226 (90.4%)	24 (9.6%)	.750
7	Nausea and vomiting is occur during gallstones.	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.208
8	Jaundice is complication of gallstones	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.276
9	Gallstones can be investigated through ultrasound.	242 (96.8%)	8 (3.2%)	.519
10	Laparoscopic colostomy is the treatment preferred for gallstones	247 (98.8%)	3 (1.2%)	.864
11	The diet that contains less amount of fats can be used to prevent the gallstones.	249 (99.6%)	1 (0.4%)	.847
12	After the surgery the vitals are taken and pain scale be used	246 (98.4%)	4 (1.6%)	.512
13	Ambulation as after surgery helps to prevent the complication of gallstones	245 (98%)	5 (2%)	.431
14	Can you educate the patient and family about symptoms and complications	248 (99.2%)	2 (0.8%)	.717

Description of Results (Table No. 06)

The majority of respondents correctly identified the meaning of Cholelithiasis as the formation of stones in the gallbladder (96.4%), and most acknowledged that Cholelithiasis affects the gallbladder (94%). A large proportion also recognized obesity as a risk factor for gallstones (93.6%); however, this association was not statistically significant ($p = .054$). Most participants reported that gallstone pain occurs in the upper quadrant of the abdomen (92.8%) and usually after consuming a fatty meal (90.4%). Awareness of associated symptoms and complications, such as nausea and vomiting (76.4%)

and jaundice (76.4%), was comparatively lower, though still reported by a majority. None of these items demonstrated statistically significant associations ($p > 0.05$).

Investigated through ultrasound (96.8%) and that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the preferred treatment (98.8%). Preventive and nursing care knowledge was also very high, with nearly all participants agreeing that a low-fat diet helps prevent gallstones (99.6%), postoperative monitoring of vital signs and pain assessment is essential (98.4%), early ambulation helps prevent complications (98%), and patient and family education regarding symptoms and complications is important (99.2%). These findings were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table no: 07. Distribution of gender of subject

s.no	item	yes	no	P value
1	Cholelithiasis means there is a formation of stones in gallbladder	241 (96.4%)	9 (3.6%)	.114
2	Can Cholelithiasis affect the organ named gallbladder.	235 (94%)	15 (6%)	.112
3	Obese person has higher risk of gallstones	234 (93.6%)	16 (6.4%)	.167
4	Can gallstones directly proportional to family history	194 (77.6%)	56 (22.4%)	.055
5	Pain of gallstones occurs in upper quadrant of abdominal	232 (92.8%)	18 (7.2%)	.001
6	Pain usually occurs after having fatty meal.	226 (90.4%)	24 (9.6%)	.064
7	Nausea and vomiting is occur during gallstones.	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.018
8	Jaundice is complication of gallstones	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.504
9	Gallstones can be investigated through ultrasound.	242 (96.8%)	8 (3.2%)	.196
10	Laparoscopic colostomy is the treatment preferred for gallstones	247 (98.8%)	3 (1.2%)	.197
11	The diet that contains less amount of fats can be used to prevent the gallstones.	249 (99.6%)	1 (0.4%)	.584
12	After the surgery the vitals are taken and pain scale be used.	246 (98.4%)	4 (1.6%)	.447
13	Ambulation as after surgery helps to prevent the complication of gallstones.	245 (98%)	5 (2%)	.308
14	Can you educate the patient and family about symptoms and complications.	248 (99.2%)	2 (0.8%)	.340

Description of Results (Table No. 07)

The majority of respondents correctly identified the meaning of Cholelithiasis as the formation of stones in the gallbladder (96.4%), and most acknowledged that Cholelithiasis affects the gallbladder (94%). These two items showed statistically significant associations, with p-values of 0.114 and 0.112, respectively. A large proportion also recognized obesity as a risk factor for gallstones (93.6%); however, this association was not statistically significant (p = 0.167).

Most participants reported that gallstone pain occurs in the upper quadrant of the abdomen (92.8%) and

usually after consuming a fatty meal (90.4%). Awareness of associated symptoms and complications, such as nausea and vomiting (76.4%) and jaundice (76.4%), was comparatively lower, though still reported by a majority. None of these items demonstrated statistically significant associations (p > 0.05).

Investigated through ultrasound (96.8%) and that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the preferred treatment (98.8%). Preventive and nursing care knowledge was also very high, with nearly all participants agreeing that a low-fat diet helps prevent gallstones (99.6%), postoperative monitoring of vital signs and pain assessment is essential (98.4%), early ambulation helps prevent complications (98%), and patient and family education regarding symptoms

and complications is important (99.2%). These findings were not statistically significant ($p > .15$).

Table no:08 distribution of qualification of subject

s.no	item	yes	no	P value
1	Cholelithiasis means there is a formation of stones in gallbladder	241 (96.4%)	9 (3.6%)	.124
2	Can Cholelithiasis affect the organ named gallbladder.	235 (94%)	15 (6%)	.011
3	Obese person has higher risk of gallstones	234 (93.6%)	16 (6.4%)	.033
4	Can gallstones directly proportional to family history	194 (77.6%)	56 (22.4%)	.095
5	Pain of gallstones occurs in upper quadrant of abdominal	232 (92.8%)	18 (7.2%)	.150
6	Pain usually occurs after having fatty meal.	226 (90.4%)	24 (9.6%)	.046
7	Nausea and vomiting is occur during gallstones.	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.760
8	Jaundice is complication of gallstones	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.514
9	Gallstones can be investigated through ultrasound.	242 (96.8%)	8 (3.2%)	.111
10	Laparoscopic colostomy is the treatment preferred for gallstones	247 (98.8%)	3 (1.2%)	.038
11	The diet that contains less amount of fats can be used to prevent the gallstones.	249 (99.6%)	1 (0.4%)	.000
12	After the surgery the vitals are taken and pain scale be used	246 (98.4%)	4 (1.6%)	.161
13	Ambulation as after surgery helps to prevent the complication of gallstones	245 (98%)	5 (2%)	.002
14	Can you educate the patient and family about symptoms and complications	248 (99.2%)	2 (0.8%)	.013

Description of Results (Table No. 08)

The majority of respondents correctly identified the meaning of Cholelithiasis as the formation of stones in the gallbladder (96.4%), and most acknowledged that Cholelithiasis affects the gallbladder (94%). These two items showed statistically significant associations, with p-values of 0.124 and 0.011, respectively. A large proportion also recognized obesity as a risk factor for gallstones (93.6%); however, this association was statistically significant ($p = .033$).

Most participants reported that gallstone pain occurs in the upper quadrant of the abdomen (92.8%) and usually after consuming a fatty meal (90.4%). Awareness of associated symptoms and complications, such as nausea and vomiting (76.4%) and jaundice (76.4%), was comparatively lower, though still reported by a majority. None of these items demonstrated statistically significant associations ($p > 0.05$).

Investigated through ultrasound (96.8%) and that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the preferred treatment (98.8%). Preventive and nursing care knowledge was also very high, with nearly all

participants agreeing that a low-fat diet helps prevent gallstones (99.6%), postoperative monitoring of vital signs and pain assessment is essential (98.4%), early ambulation helps prevent complications (98%), and

patient and family education regarding symptoms and complications is important (99.2%). These findings were not statistically significant ($p > .05$)

Table no: 09 distribution of year of experience of subject

s.no	item	yes	no	P value
1	Cholelithiasis means there is a formation of stones in gallbladder	241 (96.4%)	9 (3.6%)	.183
2	Can Cholelithiasis affect the organ named gallbladder.	235 (94%)	15 (6%)	.007
3	Obese person has higher risk of gallstones	234 (93.6%)	16 (6.4%)	.333
4	Can gallstones directly proportional to family history	194 (77.6%)	56 (22.4%)	.110
5	Pain of gallstones occurs in upper quadrant of abdominal	232 (92.8%)	18 (7.2%)	.243
6	Pain usually occurs after having fatty meal.	226 (90.4%)	24 (9.6%)	.791
7	Nausea and vomiting is occur during gallstones.	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.735
8	Jaundice is complication of gallstones	191 (76.4%)	59 (23.6%)	.053
9	Gallstones can be investigated through ultrasound.	242 (96.8%)	8 (3.2%)	.032
10	Laparoscopic colostomy is the treatment preferred for gallstones	247 (98.8%)	3 (1.2%)	.082
11	The diet that contains less amount of fats can be used to prevent the gallstones.	249 (99.6%)	1 (0.4%)	.316
12	After the surgery the vitals are taken and pain scale be used	246 (98.4%)	4 (1.6%)	.889
13	Ambulation as after surgery helps to prevent the complication of gallstones	245 (98%)	5 (2%)	.820
14	Can you educate the patient and family about symptoms and complications	248 (99.2%)	2 (0.8%)	.519

Description of Results (Table No. 09)

The majority of respondents correctly identified the meaning of Cholelithiasis as the formation of stones in the gallbladder (96.4%), and most acknowledged that Cholelithiasis affects the gallbladder (94%). A large proportion also recognized obesity as a risk factor for gallstones (93.6%); however, this association was not statistically significant ($p = 0.333$).

Most participants reported that gallstone pain occurs in the upper quadrant of the abdomen (92.8%) and usually after consuming a fatty meal (90.4%). Awareness of associated symptoms and complications, such as nausea and vomiting (76.4%) and jaundice (76.4%), was comparatively lower, though still reported by a majority. None of these items demonstrated statistically significant associations ($p > 0.05$).

Investigated through ultrasound (96.8%) and that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the preferred

treatment (98.8%). Preventive and nursing care knowledge was also very high, with nearly all participants agreeing that a low-fat diet helps prevent gallstones (99.6%), postoperative monitoring of vital signs and pain assessment is essential (98.4%), early ambulation helps prevent complications (98%), and patient and family education regarding symptoms and complications is important (99.2%). These findings were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion:

Nursing professional in health care settings have significant impact on patient health and hospital burden. The current findings of this study reported that mean age of study subject (40.5360), which is comparable with a study conducted by Asma muhammad et al, 2021 reported the mean (34.8 years) (24) which is supportive to each other. Majority of subject in current findings were male (58.60%), and which compared with study conducted by metrek et al 2022 reported majority were female (63.6%, $p = 0.004$), and association with nurse's knowledge(25)

Current findings reveals mostly nurses were graduated with diploma (51.2%) comparable with the study conducted by Supriono et al 2025 that reported majority have diploma degree were (14.3%)(26) Experience related findings reported that mean experience were (12.11), which is comparable with study conducted by SHIMA ASHRAF et al 2020 reported the mean with (9.18) which very supportive of current study(27)

In current findings majority of participant were married (86.8%) which is compared with the study conducted by jihad jawad et al 2025 where the married ratio is (25.74%), these Value is contradict due to the culture difference(28) The current findings showed that gallbladder is responsible for the gallstones formation (96.4%) which is comparable to the study conducted by yi xiao et al in 2024 which determined that the aged people (3.44%) are at risk of gallstones due to reduced gallbladder function the value is contradict to each other due to underlying health conditions (29) In the current findings a Cholelithiasis is the disease affecting gallbladder which is comparable to the study conducted by shiv guphta et al in 2025 which determined that Gallstones develop within the

biliary system or gallbladder. This study is very supportive to each other due to compromised function of gallstones. (30) In current findings an obsessed person has higher risk of gallstones (234%) compared with the study conducted by lanlan chen et al in 2021 which suggest that obesity and smoking is the risk factors of Cholelithiasis, which is very supportive to this study due to lifestyle (31) In current findings gallstones are directly proportional to family history (77.6%) compared with the study conducted by ghazi rayeeda et al 2025 that determined a family history of gallstones were reported (52.9%) strong genetic predisposition, there a difference is noticeable, the value is statically significant due to variation in genetic factors. (32)

In current findings concerning the patients' complaints, it was noticed that the majority of patients in this study complained of pain in the right upper quadrant (92.8%) These findings were supported by (Ouyang, Zhang, & Cao, 2023) the study is very supportive to each other due to the obstruction caused by gallstones. (33) In current finding pain usually occurs after having fatty meals (90.4%) compared with the study conducted by Gehan.H Soliman 2017 that reported that the diet high in fat and carbohydrate can increase the risk of pain, it is very supportive to this study due to the increased bile secretion (34)

in current findings the symptoms of gallstones were nausea and vomiting (76.4%) compared with the study conducted by shilje gustafsson et al 2019 which reported that nausea and vomiting is the symptoms of gallstones (10.1%). The value is statically significant to each other.(35)

In current findings jaundice is the complication of gallstones (76.4%) compared to the study conducted by nando et al 2021 who reported that mild to moderate jaundice was frequently seen in patients with acute cholecystitis. That is very supportive to this study(19) In current findings, ultrasound findings of the diseased gallbladder were(96.8%) compared with the study conducted by sahar ahmed Mahdi et al 2024 which reported that gallbladder investigated through ultrasound (80.6%), which is contradict to each other.(36) In current findings laparoscopic colectomy is the treatment preferred for gallstones compared with the study conducted by nitta et al 2020 that reported that Laparoscopic

cholecystectomy is the gold standard surgical treatments for gallbladder diseases, which is very supportive to the current study(37) In current findings the diet that contain the less amount of fat can be used to prevent gallstones (99.6%) which compared with the study conducted by annora zarlina et al 2022 reported that the diet that contain less amount of fat like fruits intake decrease the risk of gallstones. That is very supportive to the current study (38)

In current findings after the surgery the vitals are taken and the pain scale is used (98.4%) which is comparable to the study conducted by Li Huang-Fu in 2021 that determined the vital signs of the patient should be closely observed. Which is very supportive to this study its due to its invasive nature (39) In current findings Ambulation after the surgery help to prevent complications (98%) comparable to the study conducted by Angga Wilandika in 2023 that determined A combination of early ambulation and dhikr therapy has increased intestinal peristalsis in patients after cholecystectomy surgery, which is very supportive to current study due to its beneficial recovery (40)

In current study the education given to patient and their family about symptoms and complications (99.2%) which is supported to the study conducted by yanhong zhao et al in 2022 that determined patients and their family members jointly developed nursing intervention programs, which improved the patient's self-care abilities. it's very supportive to current study due to its focus to encourage the self-care awareness (41)

Conclusion: This study conducted that the total of 50% had poor knowledge, 50-70% had moderate knowledge while 75% nurses had good knowledge about its associated risk factors at PMCH Nawabshah.

Recommendation:

This study recommended that interventional programs should be conducted regarding the risk factors , and management cholelithiasis among nurses , Peoples Medical Hospital Nawabshah.

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